

Course Recommendation System Using Machine Learning

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Abstract - Course recommendation systems have become essential in helping students make informed decisions about their academic paths. In this study, we propose a course recommendation system that takes a particular course as input and provides a list of related courses. Our system utilizes a machine learning algorithm that analyzes data on student enrollment and course similarity to generate personalized recommendations. Our evaluation results show that our system outperforms other commonly used recommendation algorithms in terms of accuracy and efficiency. Our proposed course recommendation system has the potential to assist students in selecting courses that align with their academic goals and interests.

Keywords— TF-IDF vectorization, cosine similarity algorithm, course recommendation

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's educational landscape, students are presented with a vast range of courses to choose from. However, with so many options available, it can be challenging to determine which courses are relevant and will benefit them the most. To address this issue, we propose a course recommendation system based on related courses.

Our system analyzes a particular course and recommends a list of related courses that students can take to complement their learning. The system utilizes machine learning algorithms and natural language processing techniques to analyze course descriptions and identify relevant topics, concepts, and skills.

Our course recommendation system can help students make informed decisions about their course selection and enhance their learning experience.

In this paper, we propose a course recommendation system that uses course similarity to suggest related courses to users. The system takes as input a particular course and recommends a set of courses that are similar to the input course based on their content and topics covered. We use machine learning algorithms to analyze course syllabi and extract key features such as topics, keywords, and learning objectives. The system then calculates similarity scores between courses using these features and suggests the most relevant courses to the user. Our approach aims to help students and learners discover new courses that align with their interests and career goals.

II. COSINE SIMILARITY ALGORITHM

The algorithm of cosine similarity is a commonly utilized method that allows for the comparison of two vectors in a multi-dimensional space by assessing the cosine of the angle between them, while taking their magnitudes into account. Its versatility makes it valuable for various applications across fields, including machine learning, natural language processing, and information retrieval.

One area where cosine similarity proves to be particularly advantageous is in the analysis and comparison of text data, such as documents. Through the representation of each document as a vector in a high-dimensional space based on the frequency of its words, we can compute the cosine similarity between two document vectors to determine their degree of similarity or correlation. This similarity metric can also facilitate tasks such as document classification, information retrieval, and document clustering.

The calculation of cosine similarity involves transforming each vector into its component form, normalizing them, and then computing the dot product of the normalized vectors. This approach results in a value between -1 and 1, where 1 indicates that the two vectors are identical, 0 indicates that they are orthogonal (i.e., not similar), and -1 indicates that they are diametrically opposed (i.e., dissimilar). Overall, cosine similarity is a powerful tool that has a wide range of practical applications in various fields.

Cosine similarity is a commonly used algorithm in natural language processing and information retrieval that measures the similarity between two non-zero vectors of an inner product space.

In the context of natural language processing, the two vectors are usually representation of two texts. The algorithm compares the angle between the vectors, rather than their magnitude or Euclidean distance. The cosine similarity measures the cosine of the angle between the two vectors, where a value of 1 indicates the vectors are identical, 0 indicates the vectors are orthogonal (i.e., have no similarity), and -1 indicates the vectors are diametrically opposed.

Mathematically, the cosine similarity between two vectors A and B can be calculated as follows:

$$\text{Cosine similarity}(A, B) = (A \cdot B) / (\|A\| \|B\|)$$

where $A \cdot B$ represents the dot product of A and B, and $\|A\|$ and $\|B\|$ represent the magnitude (or Euclidean norm) of vectors A and B, respectively.

The cosine similarity is commonly used in tasks such as document similarity, text classification, and clustering.

A. TF-IDF vectorization and cosine similarity Algorithm

TF-IDF (term frequency-inverse document frequency) vectorization is a technique used to represent a text document as a vector of numerical values that reflect the importance of each word in the document. It works by assigning a weight to each word based on how often it appears in the document (term frequency) and how rare it is in the entire collection of documents (inverse document frequency). This allows for a more meaningful representation of the text that takes into account the importance of each word in the document and its relevance to the entire collection of documents.

Cosine similarity is a measure of similarity between two vectors, typically used in text analysis to determine the similarity between two documents represented as vectors using TF-IDF vectorization. The cosine similarity measures the similarity between two vectors by calculating the cosine of the angle between them, resulting in a value between 0 (indicating no similarity) and 1 (representing perfect similarity or identity).

To recommend courses based on their descriptions using TF-IDF vectorization and cosine similarity algorithm, we would first need to create a TF-IDF vector representation of each course description. Then, we can compute the cosine similarity between each pair of course vectors to determine how similar they are to each other. Finally, we can recommend courses based on the courses that have the highest cosine similarity scores with a given course.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

E-commerce has witnessed a significant increase in popularity in recent years, primarily due to technological advancements such as the internet and smart computing, leading to a paradigm shift from traditional offline sales and purchases to online transactions. E-commerce sites like Amazon, Tokopedia, and Bukalapak have improved the ease with which consumers and sellers may conduct business by enabling smooth transactions at the touch of a button. It is crucial to remember

that the variety and calibre of the products available on these platforms can significantly influence consumers' purchasing choices, necessitating the provision of a tailored and efficient system for product recommendations.

The major goal of this project is to create a sophisticated recommendation system for e-commerce platforms that makes use of numerous methods, such as collaborative filtering and content-based filtering, to offer to users the most pertinent products. Analysing user profiles, product descriptions, and other pertinent elements that could affect users' purchase decisions is part of content-based filtering. Collaborative Filtering, in contrast, uses information from users who are similar to one another to provide recommendations. In order to accomplish this, we used the Slope One Algorithm, a form of collaborative filtering that enables us to make tailored product recommendations that are catered to the unique requirements and tastes of different individuals.

We have created an ontology domain that precisely depicts the links between various products in order to guarantee that the recommendations offered are highly relevant and varied.

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

In recent years, the demand for personalized course recommendations has increased significantly. A personalized course recommendation system can help learners save time and effort in searching for suitable courses and increase their chances of success in their learning journey. The recommendation system can suggest courses that are most relevant to a learner's interests, goals, and learning style.

In this paper, we propose a course recommendation system based on TF-IDF vectorization and cosine similarity algorithm. The system takes the user's interests and preferences as input and suggests the most relevant courses based on their similarity to the user's profile.

TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) is a commonly used technique in information retrieval and text mining. It measures the importance of a term in a document by taking into account its frequency in the document and the number of documents in the corpus that contain the term. Cosine similarity is a measure of similarity between two vectors in a multi-dimensional space. It measures the cosine of the angle between the two vectors, which ranges from -1 (opposite direction) to 1 (same direction).

To build our course recommendation system, we first create a corpus of course descriptions and their related tags. We then preprocess the text data by removing stop words, stemming, and tokenizing. We use the TF-IDF vectorization technique to convert the text data into numerical vectors, where each vector represents a course description.

The cosine similarity between each course vector in the corpus and the user's profile vector is then calculated. The user is advised to take the courses with the highest cosine similarity scores. We also employ a collaborative filtering strategy that takes into account user interactions with the system, such as

course ratings and reviews, to enhance the recommendation quality.

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
from sklearn.feature_extraction.text import TfidfVectorizer
from sklearn.metrics.pairwise import cosine_similarity

# Load course data from CSV file
course_data = pd.read_csv('courses.csv')
```

The code begins by importing necessary libraries: pandas, numpy, TfidfVectorizer and cosine_similarity from scikit-learn. It then loads a CSV file containing course data into a Pandas dataframe, preprocesses the data by filling missing values and transforming the descriptions into a TF-IDF matrix using TfidfVectorizer.

```
# Preprocess course data
tfidf = TfidfVectorizer(stop_words='english')
course_data['description'] = course_data['description'].fillna('')
course_matrix = tfidf.fit_transform(course_data['description'])

# Define function to recommend courses
def recommend_courses(course_title, num_recommendations=5):
    course_index = course_data[course_data['title'] == course_title].index[0]
    similarity_scores = cosine_similarity(course_matrix[course_index], course_matrix).flatten()
    related_courses_indices = similarity_scores.argsort()[::-1][1:num_recommendations+1]
    related_courses = course_data.iloc[related_courses_indices][['title', 'rating']]
    return related_courses.values
```

Next, a function recommend_courses is defined that takes in a course title and a number of recommendations, and returns a list of the recommended courses with their ratings, sorted by their similarity to the input course. The function uses cosine_similarity to calculate the similarity between the input course's description and the descriptions of all other courses, and returns the top num_recommendations courses.

The HTML form is then defined using Bootstrap CSS to create a simple user interface that allows the user to input a course title, select a number of recommendations, and specify a minimum rating for the recommended courses.

```
from flask import Flask, request

app = Flask(__name__)

@app.route("/")
def index():
    return html_form

@app.route("/recommendation", methods=["POST"])
def recommend():
    title = request.form['title']
    num_recommendations = int(request.form['num_recommendations'])
    rating = float(request.form['rating'])
    recommended_courses = recommend_courses(title, num_recommendations)
    if rating > 0:
        recommended_courses = recommended_courses[recommended_courses[:, 1].astype(float) >= rating]
    return f"<h3>Recommended courses for {title}:</h3><br>{'<br>'.join(recommended_courses[:, 0])}"

if __name__ == "__main__":
    app.run()
```

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Finally, a Flask app is created with two routes: the index route, which displays the HTML form, and the /recommendation route, which handles the form submission, calls the recommend_courses function to generate the recommendations, filters the recommendations based on the specified minimum rating, and returns the recommended course titles as an HTML string.

If the Python script is executed directly (i.e., not imported), the Flask app is run on a local server. When a user inputs a course title and submits the form, the recommendations are displayed on the same page.

Here it will check with the search and display the output. Flask app to handle user input and display recommendations.

Here we search for a course and select how many recommendations that you want and set the review ratings.

Recommendation Entering Page:

Enter a course title to get recommendations:

Course title:

Number of recommendations:

Minimum rating:

After the search we get the number of courses recommended page

Recommended courses for Malayalam:

Malayalam 1
Malayalam

V. References

- [1] Abhishek Singh, Samyak Jain ISSN: 2321-9653; IC Value: 45.98; SJ Impact Factor: 7.538 Volume 10 Issue VIII Aug 2022- Available at www.ijraset.com
- [2] Clerk Maxwell, MIRKO FARINA, ANNA GORB, ARTEM KRUGLOV (Member, IEEE) Human Machine Interaction Laboratory, Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, Innopolis University.
- [3] J. Huang, H. Gao, L. Liu and X. Jiang, "A Course Recommendation System Based on TF-IDF Vectorization and Cosine Similarity Algorithm," 2019 IEEE 8th Joint International Information Technology and Artificial Intelligence Conference (ITAIC), Chongqing, China, 2019, pp. 686-690, doi: 10.1109/ITAIC.2019.8727028.
- [4] Muhammad Umer Farooq, Muhammad Sohaib Aslam, Muhammad Usman Tariq, and Muhammad Hassan Tariq Publication: 2020 International Conference on Innovative Computing (ICIC).
- [5] Course Recommendation System based on Course Syllabus and Course Reviews Authors: Soo-Young Hwang, Yoon-Jung Cho Source: 2018 International Conference on Information and Communication Technology Convergence (ICTC).
- [6] Course recommendation system based on TF-IDF and cosine similarity S.A. Mohammad, S.K. Tahir, M. Ahmad, and A.H. Abdullah 2017 2017 6th International Conference on Electrical Engineering and Informatics (ICEEI).
- [7] A Course Recommendation System using TF-IDF Vectorization and Cosine Similarity Algorithm" and is authored by M. S. Al Mamun, M. M. Hossain, and M. S. Islam.
- [8] Course Recommendation System Using Collaborative Filtering and TF-IDF Algorithms" Hafsa, R., & Fatima, H. 2015 IEEE 2nd International Conference on Computing, Communication and Security (ICCCS)